

DESIGN OF HEATING PANELS FOR PROTECTIVE CLOTHING

S.H. ERYURUK¹, S.K. BAHADIR¹, F. KALAOGLU¹

¹Istanbul Technical University, Textile Technologies and Design Faculty, Istanbul, Turkey
kursuns@itu.edu.tr

Abstract: *One of the prime functions of the wearing behavior of humans is to obtain the most appropriate thermal environmental conditions that ensure the needs of thermal balance and thermal comfort according to the working environment. In this study the design of heating panels based on e-textile design concepts is aimed. The e-textile architecture of the heating panels was formed using stainless steel conductive yarn. The electrical circuit network on the textile structure was successfully embedded via sewing technique. Different kinds of fabrics were combined in order to obtain functional protective clothing system. Fabric system consists of five layers: first layer is outer fabric made from PBI fiber, second layer is moisture barrier fabric from hydrophilic polyester membrane laminated on to a polyester raschel knitted fabric, third layer is conductive yarn embedded thermal barrier fabric, the fourth layer is again moisture barrier fabric from hydrophilic polyester membrane and the fifth layer is thermal barrier fabric. The fabric system was tested for thermal comfort properties as well as for heating function*

Keywords: *e-textiles, protective clothing, heating panels, stainless steel*

1. Introduction

The protective clothing refers the various suits and uniforms worn to protect the user from any hazards. The purpose of the protective clothing is to protect user to hazards when engineering and administrative controls or the environment are not feasible or effective to decrease occurring risks to acceptable levels.

Recently, there is on-going research in the integration of sensing functionality into traditional textile structures and these new textile products integrated with sensing properties may be defined as smart textiles, intelligent textiles, or functional textiles. Electronic textiles (e-textiles) defined in the area of smart textiles, are the combination of textile materials with electronics and specific technological materials. In other words, if the textile structure includes an electric circuit within itself, then it takes place in the category of e-textiles [1-3].

Heating panels can be useful in protective clothing when the employee works in cold weather conditions. As a fabric heating element, one possible option is to use conductive yarns inside the fabric structure to develop electrical circuit in the fabric. However, uniform distribution and dissipation of heat are unique characteristics for performance of the heating structures that should be well controlled by the location of heating elements in a close proximity to the heated area. Electrical resistance heating is any process in which electrical energy is transferred to heat. When electric current is passed through a conductive material, the resistance it encounters leads the material to heat up. Depending on the fabric structure and the used materials as well as power source and system configuration, the heating capacity of the fabric changes. Moreover, the selection of the appropriate conductive yarn with a base yarn is a crucial issue since the voltage applied on the conductive yarn causes fabric to be heated. In the literature, it is seen that there are many studies about e-textiles particularly dealing with the usage of conductive yarns [4, 5]. In some studies, conductive yarns presenting electrical function for heating purposes have been presented. For instance, Li et al. [6] used silver-coated yarn to produce conductive knitted fabric with specific stitches, which can be used for intelligent applications such as monitoring and heat generation. Hamdani et al. [7] studied the thermo-mechanical properties of knitted structures designed by using silver-coated Nylon 6,6 filaments. Similarly, Sezgin et al. investigated the heating behavior of silver conductive threads through woven structures [8]. Moreover, Kayacan et al. investigated the functionality of heating panels using stainless steel yarns [9].

In this study, the design of heating panels based on electrical resistance heating approach is aimed. The e-textile circuit of the heating panels was formed using stainless steel conductive yarn. Different kinds of fabrics were combined in order to obtain functional heating panels for protective clothing. The layered fabric system was tested for thermal resistance, water vapour resistance, air permeability properties as well as for heating function.

2. Experimental work

2.1 Materials

In this study, fabric system consists of five layers are combined together in order to design heating panel for protective clothing. The first layer is outer fabric made from PBI fiber, second layer is moisture barrier fabric from hydrophilic polyester membrane laminated onto a polyester raschel knitted fabric, third layer is conductive yarn embedded thermal barrier fabric, the fourth layer is again moisture barrier fabric from hydrophilic polyester membrane and the fifth layer is thermal barrier fabric. The characteristic of fabrics are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of fabrics

Layer	Fabric details
1st layer	OUTER FABRIC <i>PBI Matrix 200 g/m²</i>
2nd layer	MOISTURE BARRIER <i>PU Membrane which is laminated to knitted fabric (85g/ m²)</i>
3rd layer	HEAT BARRIER LAMINATED WITH CONDUCTIVE YARN <i>Aramid Viscose FR inner lining quilted to nonwoven (55g/ m²)</i>
4th layer	MOISTURE BARRIER <i>PU Membrane which is laminated to knitted fabric (85g/ m²)</i>
5th layer	HEAT BARRIER <i>Aramid Viscose inner lining quilted to Aramid felt</i>

The electrical circuit in the structure was formed over the 3rd layer using stainless steel with a linear resistance of <10 ohm/m. The linear resistance of the conductive yarn was measured in ohm per meter (ohm/m) using a TTI 1906 computing multimeter. In order to integrate conductive yarn into textile structure, flat sewing machine was used. The 3rd layer with conductive yarn is shown in Fig.1

Figure 1. The 3rd layer with conductive yarn

2.2 Measurements

The samples were tested for thermal comfort properties as well as for heating function. In order to test the thermal properties of samples, all the fabrics first were placed on a flat surface for at least 24 h prior to testing under standard atmospheric conditions (65%±2% RH, 20°C±2°C). Thermal resistance of samples was determined with Permetest machine (Figure 2a) and Water vapour resistance of samples was also determined with Permetest machine with adding pure water to the machine. Prowhite Air Permeability Tester Machine was used in order to test air permeability of the samples (Figure 2b.). Tests were done according to ISO Standards (under 400 kPa).

Figure 2. Thermal resistance and air permeability tests

To carry out thermal analysis, thermal camera (from Testo Inc., Thermal Imager Testo 885) and DC power supply were used. The required energy to e-fabric samples was provided from DC power supply. Voltage supplied from DC power supply was increased starting from 5V to 15V with an increment of 5V.

3. Results

Electrical conductivity test was applied on conductive yarns which are sewed to heat barrier fabric and it was measured using multimeter. Length of conductive yarn on the fabric was obtained 173.5 cm for the design. Characteristics of the selected conductive yarn is seen in Table 2. The conductivity was measured as 14.52 Ω/m .

Table 2. Characteristics of the conductive yarn

Yarn type	Linear Resistance (ohm/m)	Yarn Count (Nm)	Fiber Type
1	<10	3	Stainless-Steel

Thermal resistance, water vapour resistance and air permeability tests were conducted (Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5). It was observed that layered e-textile samples has high thermal and water vapour resistance and air permeability values. High thermal resistance is required to meet the thermal isolation after the heating panels are activated. Because fabric system consists of five layers, high water vapour resistance values were obtained. Moreover, acceptable air permeability results were obtained considering PU membrane moisture barrier which was used in the second and fourth layers inside the five layered structure.

Table 3. Thermal Resistance Results

Thermal Resistance Results (Mkm ² /W)	CV	Standard Deviation
117.8	5.7	6.7146

Table 4. Water Vapour Resistance Results

Water Vapour Resistance Results	CV	Standard Deviation
34.5	71	24.495

Table 5. Air Permeability Results

Air permeability Results (mm/s)	CV	Standard Deviation
401.00	71.75653	17.8944

Thermal Imager Testo 885 was used to measure temperature distribution at four different voltages as 0-5-10-15 V respectively. Figure 3 shows the thermal camera test results. When 5 V voltage was applied, 25.6 °C temperature was obtained in the textile structure. 37 °C was observed with 10 V voltage and 56.3 °C temperature was obtained with 15V. As a result it was obtained that 10 V is adequate to use for the designed structure.

Figure 3. Thermal camera test results

4. Conclusions

This study aimed designing of a heating panel on the protective clothing with e-textile infrastructure. For this purpose, first of all protective clothing type and fabric layers were specified. Then conductive yarn type and the identification of circuit design of conductive yarn into the fabric layers were decided. Produced e-textile structure was subjected to some tests for functional requirements such as electrical conductivity, thermal resistance, air permeability, water vapour permeability and thermal camera tests. As a result of the study it was observed that designed e-textile structure meet the functional requirements adequately.

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